

MANUFACTURING AND MECHANICAL TESTING OF A RIB IN THERMOPLASTIC RESIN AND ITS COMPARISON WITH THE CURRENT THERMOSET DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

A technique for APC-2 processing has been developed based on a diaphragm method carried out in 'cold' autoclave. The whole assembly composite material and tooling, is heated using I.R. heaters while the autoclave is only used as pressurization vessel.

Results show that although the postbuckling capability of the PEEK/AS4 material is higher than the postbuckling capability of the F-593/T300, a weight penalty of a 27 % is obtained respect to the same rib manufactured in thermoset resin. Cost analysis drive to the conclusion that 40 % of price reduction in APC-2 material would be needed to get a competitive manufacturing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Material selection plays an importance role in the final cost of the structure. In general, thermoplastic materials offer some potential advantages over thermoset. Their main advantages and disadvantages are shown in table 1.

Table 1 : Advantages and disadvantages of thermoplastics.

Advantages	Disadvantages
greater toughness	high processing temperature
high service temperature	poor chemical resistance
shorter fabrication cycle	limited processing experience
no refrigeration for storage	lack of material database
good processing capabilities	
reparability	
reprocessing (postformable)	
reusability of scraps and rejected pieces	

The best way to determine the feasibility of the thermoplastic materials in primary structures is to balance all these factors within the development of a composite element. This will allow to establish some basis for manufacturing cost and weights, which are the main design parameters when building structures.

With the aim to evaluate the manufacturability, cost effectively and weight effect of thermoplastics, CASA decided at the beginning of this decade to validate their suitability for primary structures with the design, production and testing of the rib 10 of the Airbus A320 Horizontal Stabilizer. The material selected was a polyetheretherketone (PEEK) resin with AS4 reinforcements, being the current production series design in F-593/T300 thermoset material.

This paper presents, as a summary, the results and conclusion of such research program.

2 DEVELOPMENT OF MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUE

A technique for APC-2 (PEEK/AS4) processing has been developed based on a double diaphragm method carried out in 'cold' autoclave. Fig. 1 shows a sketch of the assembly used for ribs manufacturing.

Fig. 1 : APC-2 manufacturing assembly for double diaphragm forming.

A system to heat the forming assembly within the autoclave was designed and installed. Quartz IR panels with medium wave emitters (750 W) were selected to heat both laminate and mould. Efficiency of the system to heat steel mould without extra operations on its surface was shown.

Four control areas were established in every IR panel and controlled by thermocouples located in the surface of the top diaphragm film or in the bottom surface of the tool. These thermocouple locations were appropriate as it was demonstrated before in several heating trials where thermocouples were placed inside the laminate and other different locations along the whole assembly.

The eight controllers were programmed to fit one constant heating rate. The highest heating rate able to provide an even distribution of temperature in the whole arrangement was selected.

Emitters' power was automatically regulated by the thermocouples measure as its control point.

Cooling phase was accomplished by natural convection. Measurement of APC-2 crystallinity in different selected areas of the formed parts was carried out by DSC to study the suitability of the method.

The designed control system for the individual heating emitters is considered as 'universal' since it can be installed in any autoclave or pressurization vessel to heat different laminate and tooling arrangements and geometries. No additional treatment of tooling surface is needed and part manufacture can be performed without previous calibration or lamp's power adjustment.

Optimization was carried out to obtain the shorter cycle yielding even temperature distribution of the whole forming arrangement (diaphragms, APC-2 plies and tool) as well as consolidated parts. Heating rates of 30° C/min were used while dwell times were comprised between 5 to 30 minutes (dwell temperatures between 380 and 400° C).

The influence of the pressure profile in combination with temperature profile versus time was investigated. Diaphragm behaviour played a very important role when optimizing pressure conditions. Autoclave pressures ranging between 0 to 6 bars were tested. Heating and pressurizing simultaneously, heating followed by pressure consolidation before forming (venting of tool cavity to the atmosphere 5 minutes after reaching dwell pressure) and heating followed by pressure-forming before consolidation (vacuum at tool cavity at the same time than autoclave pressurization) were performed in different trials with the main objective of avoiding diaphragm failure.

Upilex R properties has been found as very critical for APC-2 processing. In case of complicated parts and deep moulds, diaphragm behaviour drives cycle selection.

Parts quality were controlled by ultrasonic methods. C-scan (flat areas) and A-scan (curved areas) were obtained from the transmission, reflectant plate and pulse-echo techniques. Microscopy, chemical digestion (voids content) and DSC (crystallinity) test were carried out to analyze parts quality on cut out of strategic part locations.

Good quality parts are obtained by applying 6 bars autoclave pressure in a cycle of 45 minutes (compared with 300 minutes of thermoset cycle) and pressurization rate of 0.1 bars/min.

3 TEST SPECIMENS

The rib geometry is shown in Fig 2. The rib web is a 12-ply laminate with the following lay-up : $(45/-45/90/-45/45/0)_S$. Typical lamina elastic properties for this thermoplastic system are given in table 2 ([1]).

Fig. 2 : Geometry of test specimens

Table 2 : Typical lamina properties of material APC-2 (PEEK/AS4)

Density (Kg/m^3)	1595
Fibre volume (%)	56
Tensile modulus (GPa)	137
Compr. modulus (GPa)	112
Shear modulus G_{TL} (GPa)	5.0
Consolidated thickness (mm)	0.125

The specimens were manufactured without artificial defects being the actual thickness 1.8 mm. The quality inspection detected some manufacturing defects corresponding to small wrinkles along the specimen surface.

Before testing the specimens were impacted with the threshold impact energy (energy which produces barely visible damages). This energy was fixed at 15 J. The instrumentation was comprised of four strain gauges and two rosettes per specimen. Both were tested at RT/AR conditions in CASA Structural Test Facilities.

Shear loads were introduced in specimens, through a shear frame, by applying tension loads in one diagonal of the frame. The load was applied by steps until failure occurred.

4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The summary of the test results is shown in table 3 ([2]).

Table 3 : Tests results summary.

THERMOPLASTIC RESIN				
MATERIAL			APC-2 (PEEK/AS4)	
SPECIMEN CODE			COST-10 N.5	COST-10 N.7
IMPACT ENERGY			15 J.	15 J.
TEST CONDITION			RT/AR	RT/AR
ARTIFICIAL DEFECTS			NO	NO
THICKNESS WEB (mm)			1.8	1.8
Buckling	Initial load	(N)	55000	45000
	Flow	(N/mm)	91.2	74.6
	Stress	(N/mm ²)	50.7	41.5
Failure	load	(N)	76930	67640
	Flow	(N/mm)	127.6	112.2
	Stress	(N/mm ²)	70.9	62.3
POSTBUCKLING CAPABILITY			1.40	1.50
FAILURE MODE			DIAGONAL TENSION	

It can be observed a great difference between the test values of the two specimens manufactured with the APC-2 material (22 % at buckling and 14 % at failure). It could be due to the above mentioned manufactured defects in the specimen N.7 where the wrinkles were situated in the dimpled areas.

The test performed on A320 Horizontal Stabilizer test programme with the same subcomponent manufactured in thermoset resin with carbon fiber (F-593/T300) gave the results shown in table 4 ([3]).

The average buckling stress of the specimens manufactured with F-593/T300 material is a 13 % higher than the buckling stress of specimens manufactured with APC-2 material.

Table 4 : Tests results summary.

THERMOSET RESIN						
MATERIAL			F-593/T300			
SPECIMEN CODE			RIB 10-3	RIB 10-4	RIB 10-5	RIB 10-6
IMPACT ENERGY			NO	NO	5 J.	5 J.
TEST CONDITION			RT/AR	RT/AR	HOT/WET	HOT/WET
ARTIFICIAL DEFECTS			NO	NO	YES	YES
THICKNESS WEB (mm)			1.44	1.44	1.44	1.44
Buckling	Initial load	(N)	47060	50960	45050	41150
	Flow	(N/mm)	78.1	84.5	76.4	68.2
	Stress	(N/mm ²)	54.2	58.7	53.1	47.4
Failure	load	(N)	62180	59720	55810	64720
	Flow	(N/mm)	103.1	99.0	92.6	107.3
	Stress	(N/mm ²)	71.6	68.7	64.3	74.5
POSTBUCKLING CAPABILITY			1.32	1.17	1.21	1.57
FAILURE MODE			DIAGONAL TENSION			

Tension and compression cracks around the lightening hole are produced in the failure of the specimens. The strains at the edge of the hole corresponding to the failure of the thermoplastic and thermoset specimens are represented in table 5. The tension strains values are the mean values between the strains measured in the tension diagonal, and the compression strains are the maximum value registered in the strain gauges of the compression diagonal.

Table 5 : Test results comparison.

Specimen Code	Buckling stress (N/mm^2)	Failure stress (N/mm^2)	Tension strain ($\mu\epsilon$)	Compression strain ($\mu\epsilon$)
RIB10-5	53.1	64.3	6000	-7100
RIB10-6	47.4	74.5	7700	-7125
COST-10 N.5	50.7	70.9	7000	-10000
COST-10 N.7	41.5	62.3	8200	-9500

All the specimens tested show a postbuckling capability ratio between failure load and buckling load. The largest postbuckling capability corresponded to the APC-2 material (45 %), being however a 25% for the thermoset resin.

5 THERMOPLASTIC VERSUS THERMOSET DESIGN

With the above test results and the density of the materials, it is possible to compare the weight of the ribs manufactured with the different materials. Two different approaches will be followed to make the comparison.

In the first approach, an equivalent thickness is calculated so that all the ribs give the same buckling load (buckling load of the ribs manufactured with thermoset resin is considered as the reference). The mean value obtained for the hot/wet tests of the thermoset ribs were used.

The PEEK equivalent thickness will be determined by :

$$P_{buckling} = K \cdot t^3$$

$$t'_{PEEK} \approx t_{PEEK} \cdot \left(\frac{P_{buckling_{F-593}}}{P_{buckling_{PEEK}}} \right)^{1/3} = 1.8 \cdot \left(\frac{43600}{50000} \right)^{1/3} = 1.72 \text{ mm}$$

and the equivalent weight per surface unit ($t \cdot \rho$) will be :

$$W_{F-593} = 1.44 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot 1.45 = .209 \text{ g/cm}^2$$

$$W_{PEEK} = 1.72 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot 1.59 = .273 \text{ g/cm}^2$$

The ribs manufactured with thermoset resin, are the lightest, being the weight penalty a 30 % for PEEK/AS4 material.

In the second approach, web postbuckling is allowed and assuming the postbuckling capability obtained in tests, a new equivalent thickness could be calculated so that

all the ribs have the same failure load (failure load of the ribs manufactured with thermoset resin is considered as the reference).

The new PEEK equivalent thickness will be :

Postbuckling capability F-593/T300 rib (PC_{F-593}): 1.32

Postbuckling capability APC-2 rib (PC_{PEEK}): 1.45

$$P_{failure} = P_{buckling} \cdot PC$$

$$t''_{PEEK} \approx t_{PEEK} \cdot \left(\frac{PC_{F-593} \cdot P_{buckling_{F-593}}}{PC_{PEEK} \cdot P_{buckling_{PEEK}}} \right)^{1/3} = 1.8 \cdot \left(\frac{1.32 \cdot 43600}{1.45 \cdot 50000} \right)^{1/3} = 1.67 \text{ mm}$$

and the equivalent weight per surface unit will be :

$$W_{F-593} = 1.44 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot 1.45 = .209 \text{ g/cm}^2$$

$$W_{PEEK} = 1.67 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot 1.59 = .265 \text{ g/cm}^2$$

Again the ribs manufactured with thermoset resin are the lightest, being the weight penalty in this case a 27 % for PEEK/AS4 material.

Moreover, an analysis of costs for the manufacturing of the A320 rib 10 by using the new technique drives to the conclusion that 40 % of price reduction in APC-2 material would be needed to get a competitive manufacturing.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn when comparing the rib number 10 of the Airbus A320 Horizontal Stabilizer made of APC-2 thermoplastic resin and made of F-593/T300 series production thermoset material :

- Heating the material inside the autoclave by using IR emitters reduces the cycle time, being the main advantage of the thermoplastic matrix. Heating can be locally controlled.
- Autoclave cycle for APC-2 parts manufacturing is 15% of the cycle time needed for epoxy curing at 180° C with the developed method, but lay up operation is more time consuming.
- The average buckling stress of the specimens manufactured with F-593/T300 material is a 13 % higher than the buckling stress of specimens manufactured with APC-2 material, being their thickness 1.4 and 1.6 mm, respectively.
- Failure stress of F-593/T300 material is a 5% larger than the APC-2 failure stress but this one presents a failure strains larger than the thermoset material.

- The largest postbuckling capability corresponded to the APC-2 material (45 %), being a 25% for the thermoset resin.
- Failure mode of the materials is similar : Diagonal tension failure with tension and compression cracks around the hole.
- If the buckling load is taking as design load, the ribs manufactured with thermoset resin, are the lightest, being the weight penalty a 30 % for PEEK/AS4 material.
- If web postbuckling is allowed, the ribs manufactured with thermoset resin, are the lightest, being the weight penalty a 27 % for PEEK/AS4 material.
- An analysis of costs for the manufacturing of the rib by using the new technique drives to the conclusion that 40 % of price reduction in APC-2 material would be needed to get a competitive manufacturing.

7 REFERENCES

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